

PER AS 472 .A84 v.3

Journal of the Asiatic
Society of Bengal

LIBRARY

RL

OF THE

Theological Seminary.

PRINCETON, N. J.

Case

Drawer

I

Shelf

Section

5

Book

THE
JOURNAL
OF
THE ASIATIC SOCIETY
OF
BENGAL.

VOL. III.

THE
JOURNAL
OF
THE ASIATIC SOCIETY
OF
BENGAL.

EDITED BY
JAMES PRINSEP, F. R. S.
SECRETARY OF THE AS. SOC., AND HON. MEM. OF THE AS. SOC. OF PARIS.

VOL. III.

JANUARY TO DECEMBER,
1834.

“ It will flourish, if naturalists, chemists, antiquaries, philologers, and men of science, in different parts of *Asia*, will commit their observations to writing, and send them to the Asiatic Society at Calcutta ; it will languish, if such communications shall be long intermitted ; and it will die away, if they shall entirely cease.”

SIR WM. JONES.

Calcutta :

PRINTED AT THE BAPTIST MISSION PRESS, CIRCULAR ROAD.

SOLD BY MESSRS. THACKER AND CO., ST. ANDREW'S LIBRARY.

1834.

JOURNAL

OF

THE ASIATIC SOCIETY.

No. 27.—March, 1834.

I.—*A Description, with Drawings, of the Ancient Stone Pillar at Allahabad called Bhim Sn's Gad or Club, with accompanying copies of four inscriptions engraven in different characters upon its surface. By Lieut. T. S. Burt, Engineers.*

[Read at the meeting of the 26th December 1833.]

IN compliance with your request made some time since, that I would prepare copies of the characters engraven on an ancient pillar lying in the Fort of Allahabad, I have much pleasure in forwarding them, together with a geometrical and an explanatory drawing of the stone, (Plate III. et. seq.), which shew the situations occupied by each of the characters on the upper surface, as well as sections and elevations of the capital, which lies detached near to the top of the shaft.

The column tapers from the base to the capital from a diameter at the former of three feet two and quarter inches, to two feet two inches at the latter; the circumference of the first mentioned part is about ten feet one inch, and of the last, six feet six and a quarter inches. This was about the size of the Delhi *lath* of FIROZ SHAH, which is stated to be ten feet four in circumference, and thirty-seven feet long, [see As. Res. vol. VII. p. 178;] the shaft of this one being thirty-five, and its total length, including the base, forty-two feet seven inches.

It appears to be a hard kind of red sandstone, nearly approaching to freestone, (and not granite,) and bears a kind of silvery bed in it, which accounts for its having peeled off at several places as hereafter noticed.

The common legend of the natives states the pillar to be the *gad* or staff of BHIM SN. It may be hardly necessary to state, that BHIM

SEN was the second brother of Raja YUDHISTHIRA, or JUDISTHIR, (Shakespear's Hindoo Dictionary, page 149, of the year 1817,) whom KISHN or BISHN protected; now KRISHNA, the Apollo of the Hindoos, appears from page 599 to have lived, according to Colonel WILFORD, about 1300 years before Christ.

It is said to be the staff, with which he ground his bhang, and that the *bundi* or vessel in which the bhang was ground, was thrown into the Jumna on our taking possession of the fort. It is reported that this pillar was formerly standing near to its present position in the circular ring facing the gateway on the inside of this fort, and that it was taken down on the Fort undergoing alterations, which appears to have occurred in the 44th year of the reign of SHAH AULUM, when the plan of the fort is stated to have been altered by the English; [see page 34 of Shakespear's Hindustani Selections from the *Khelásat-ul-tauvarikh*, or Abridgment of History;] SHAH AULUM the second, came to the throne in A. D. 1761 (Hamilton's India, volume I. p. 410) so that by adding 43 years we shall bring the date of the transfer up to 1804, which was then the period of alteration of the Fort, and as is reported, of pulling down the pillar, but I have lately heard that this took place in 1798 or 99.

The capital of the column (shewn in the accompanying drawings) appears to have formerly borne a four-footed animal sitting upon it, and the slight traces remaining have the appearance of the Bull which is generally attendant upon Mahadeva. The animal must have been evidently "couchant," for the remains of the body as well as of the legs are connected to the stone itself.

The capital has a circular hole in it, probably to allow of the entrance of a point bar for fixing it on the top of the shaft, in the centre of which a similar hole is cut for that purpose.

The base of the shaft has a couple of projections similar to the trunnions of a piece of ordnance, intended probably as a place of fixture for the ropes which might be used in erecting it, or otherwise as a hold when built into its bed of masonry.

Taking the specific gravity of the block at less than that of marble and hard stone, 2.650, the weight of it will be found on calculation to be about 17 tons, 12 cwt. or 493 *mans*.

It is to be regretted that so handsome a column should be allowed to lie as it now does "unnoticed and unknown," when the outlay of about two thousand rupees would place it upon a neat pedestal in a more appropriate position, as it is represented to have stood formerly in the sketch in the Asiatic Researches. The pedestal should of course be constructed entirely after the native method of architecture, and have nothing Eu-

ropean at all in its composition, unless an incongruous effect were the desideratum of architectural beauty*.

My brother of the 64th regiment, was kind enough (for it was a work of labor) to make a copy of so much of the various characters as is situated on the present upper surface of the stone (or *gadú* as it is named by the natives). Lieut. BURT having to rejoin his corps before the stone could be removed, I have employed a moonshee in effecting a copy of the part which remained under ground, for the stone was buried about a foot in the soil, partly from the effect of its weight, and partly from the pathway having been added to from time to time with road material. I have examined each of the copies (with the stone?), and corrected the shapes of those letters which appeared to require it both in the first copy and in its transcript.

The Persian inscription is so far peculiar, that in reading it upon the stone, the lower, or second line, is to be read first, so as to preserve the gradation of the nine Emperors of Delhi mentioned in it, TIMUR being the first, and JEHANGIR the last, in whose time it would seem to have been engraved. The year mentioned is 1014 (see compartment 2 from the left, vol. VII. page 180, Asiatic Researches), which appears on reference to Mr. SMITH's Chronological Table, at page 447 of the same volume, to have been the year in which JEHANGIR was crowned at Agra.

I do not send an exact copy of the ornament surrounding the Persian inscription, as that shewn in the volume referred to is so much more neatly done than any I could obtain that I beg to refer you to it: only one or two of the Persian letters differ from the copy now sent; they are in alto relievo, beautifully cut, and still appear as if newly executed upon the pillar.

The Persian letters being in alto relievo upon the central band of the stone, induced me to think that they must have been cut or left upon it on its first removal from the quarry, or in A. H. 1014 (A. D. 1605), as above noticed; but subsequent inspections induced me to think differently, for although the letters themselves are in alto relievo, or projecting far beyond the belt or zone upon which they rest, yet the plane of that belt or zone is excavated so deeply in the periphery of the stone that its depth is exactly equal to the height of the letters themselves, which shews without contradiction that the Persian inscription could have been engraved subsequently to the writing in the Sanscrit character, every letter of which is cut into the stone, and consequently has no projection whatever, excepting what the surface of the periphery pre-

* Major IRVINE, Engineers, C. B. states that in 1826, he sent in an estimate to put it up for about 1800 rupees, but the Governor General, Lord AMHERST, objected to the expence on the grounds of its inutility!

sents at the interstices of the letters, whereas; if the sunken zone did not exist upon which the Persian characters stand prominently forth, and if the letters stood out beyond the general surface of the column itself, it might be reasonably assumed that the projecting Persian characters were coeval with the extraction of the stone from the quarry, or at least with the date of its receiving the final smoothing and polishing from its rough hewn state.

Measuring with a string I have perceived that the writer's name in Persian, ABDULLAH, in alto relievo in a separate compartment is likewise situated below the general surface of the stone: moreover, that it has been cut out at a part where the ancient inscription No. 2 had evidently peeled off before the Persian was written. This establishes the prior existence of the engravings Nos. 1 and 2, of which however, and without this proof, there could be no doubt. The same remark applies to the whole of the Persian inscription.

The Persian inscription runs thus, in the original, and rendered into Roman characters; each compartment of letters being read first from the lower line, as before explained.

الله اكبر * نورالدين محمد جهانگير بادشاه غازي * يا حافظ * ابن اكبر
 بادشاه غازي * ياحفيظ * ابن همايون بادشاه غازي * ياحي * ابن بابر
 بادشاه غازي * ياقيوم * ابن عمر شيخ ميرزا * يامقتدر * ابن سلطان
 ابوسعيد يانور * ابن سلطان محمد ميرزا * ياهادي * ابن مير
 انشاه * يابديع ابن امير تيمور صاحب قران * ياقادر * احد الهي
 شهر يورماه * موافق ربيع الثاني 1014

Allah Akbar—Nooruddin Muhammed Jehangir Badshah Gházi—ya háfiz—Ibn Akbar Badshah Gházi—ya hafeez—Ibn Humáyun Badshah Gházi—ya hay—Ibn Bábar Badshah Gházi—ya kayum—Ibn Umar Shaikh Mirza—ya MuktaDIR—Ibn Sultan Abu Said—ya nur—Ibn Sultan Muhammed Mirza—ya hadi—Ibn Miran Shah—ya badia—Amir Timur Sahib-kiran—ya kadir—ahad illahi, sahr—yur mah muafik rabiussani, 1014 (A. H.)

Translation.

(God is great!)—The light of the religion of Muhammed, the Emperor JEHANGIR, victorious over infidels;—(Oh! Preserver)—son of the Emperor AKBER, conqueror of infidels;—(Oh! Protector)—son of the Emperor HUMAYUN, victorious over infidels;—(Oh! Giver of Life)—son of the Emperor BABER, victorious, &c.;—(Oh! Eternal)—son of UMAR SHAIKH MIRZA;—(Oh! Almighty)—son of Sultan ABU SEID;—(Oh! Light)—son of Sultan MUHAMMED MIRZA;—(Oh! Guide)—son of MIRANSHAH;—(Oh! Wonderful)—son of Amir TIMUR, Lord of happy destiny;—(Oh! Omnipotent)—In the month *shahr yur*, in the 1st *Iláhl*, corresponding with *Rabiussání* A. H. 1014*.

* The *Iláhl* year should be 49, for the æra of AKBER commenced with his reign, in the 5th *Rabi-ussání* 963 (= 1 March, 1605); therefore the word احد must be a

With respect to the specimen of the inscription on the pillar at Allahabad (shewn at page 180, volume VII. As. Res.) I beg to say that, that part which originally, or when it was copied in June 1797, was adjacent to the Persian writer's name "ABDULLAH," no longer exists, and has evidently peeled off; some of the letters I can find to agree, both of the stone and the specimen, but only a few, as most of the others are manifestly incorrect, as may be seen by comparing the specimen with the full copy now sent; the former should therefore be only looked upon as a partly correct and partly incorrect specimen of the character chosen here and there, and not as an exact copy of any part of the inscription; indeed, the line in this character which is situated above the Persian in Captain HOARE'S specimen, does not now appear upon the column at all.

The inscription No. 1, (which is evidently of the same character with that upon the *lat, h* at Delhi,) is in many parts illegible, chiefly because the outer surface of the stone has peeled off to the depth of one-eighth or one-fifth of an inch from those parts, caused probably in the first instance by the effect of the hammer and chisel, or other instrument used in engraving the inscription, so as to have either cracked or loosened the general surface to the depth of the letters cut; which surface, although not at the time apparently injured, might have become, in suffering frequent alternations of heat, cold and damp, so loose in some parts, as at last to peel and fall off in flakes.

The natives state, some that the unknown character is Marhatta, others that it is Punjâbi, and that although no one at this place can now read it, a traveller from Bombay took a copy of it some years ago, and said that he could read and decipher the character; I requested my brother to make inquiries at Benares, and I have also written to Cawnpur, near to which the Mahratta Prince BAJEE RAO is stationed, with a hope of procuring information, but without effect.

The size of the letters of the ancient Sanserit character No. 2, was about an inch in height and an inch more or less in breadth, and of the unknown character No. 1, nearly the same.

One part of the unknown character No. 1 similar in every respect to that on the Delhi *lat, h*, is situated above the Persian writing on the left hand side of the drawing No. 1. and consists of but a small portion of the different letters engraven on the stone.

wrong reading for ۱۶۹. *Shahryur* is the 6th month, and falls in August. The H_{21} *ijri* also, *Rabi-ussani* 1014, corresponds with the same month. AKBER died on the 13th of *Rabi-us sani* 1014, (= 21 August, 1605;) he inscription therefore must have been cut within a few days of this event;—the coronation of JEKANGIR did not take place till *Jamâd* 2, or two months later.—ED.

Sir C. MALET, at page 384, vol. vi. *As. Res.* speaks of Hindoo symbols in Bombay, does he thereby refer to the characters of the inscription? It is not impossible indeed that they may be of a numerical or astronomical character, as hidden to our knowledge as are the Egyptian hieroglyphics, for the square, triangle, circle, mercury, are to be frequently met with in the character No. 1.

My brother in passing Benares sent a specimen of the character No. 1, to the secretary of the Hindoo College there; but that officer was unable to give any assistance in deciphering it. Lieut. B. from Benares says, "I have made every inquiry regarding the inscription, No. 1, on the pillar, a specimen of which I took with me from Allahabad; but neither the head pundit of the Pátsála here, nor any others to whom I have shewn it, are able to decipher it, or to tell me of what character it is composed."

It is very evident that the inscription, No. 1. is of exactly the same kind as that shewn in Plates X. XI. XII. XIII. and XIV. of the 7th volume *As. Res.* p. 180, as existing on the Delhi pillar, the translation of which will not I trust be considered as hopeless; but of No. 2, to which the Gya inscription is so near an approximation, Dr. MILL, Mr. CSOMA DE KÖRÖS, or any other Sanscrit scholar, will most probably be kind enough to supply the translation.

The Devanagari character, No. 3, has been also copied and is sent herewith, but it is by no means so neatly engraven on the stone as the other characters, nor is it in many places at all legible, although as an assistance in the operation we threw common red soorkee or brick-dust into the hollows which compose the letters, and then wiped off the particles that rested on the projections, between them, with a wet or rather a damp piece of cloth, which rendered the letters more distinctly visible.

This third inscription, No. 3, occupies the greatest part of the surface of the stone, and lies above the Persian. It is supposed to have been written by various persons, who in paying visits to the pillar from distant countries, left impressions of their names and actions upon the face of it. This is the native idea on the subject, but the point may be set to rest upon the character being translated. I have not made much inquiry about the legibility of the last mentioned character, as the native account took away from the interest that it would have otherwise occasioned: the letters are badly cut, and in many places almost illegible. This character, No. 3, contains some dates which I have marked: one of the year Samvat 1562; which as this is 1890 of the same era of Vikramajít, must have been written 328 years since; another of Samvat 1663, or 327 years; another 1515, or 368 years; another Samvat 1639, 261 years; another

1640, or 250 years; another 1762, or 128 years; another 1863, or 27 years; another Samvat 1638, or 252 years since.

On examining all the 18 volumes of the *As. Res.* I am happy to say I have found, or at least partly found a key to the character No. 2, in the transcript and interpretation of an ancient inscription at Gya, by Dr. WILKINS, vol. I. page 279. This will evidently serve as a guide, by which nearly half of the letters can be made out, as is evident on inspection; and it may therefore be assumed as likely that Dr. WILKINS at home, or any Sanscrit scholar in this country, has in his possession means of reading and translating the whole of this at present unknown inscription, No. 2; which from what the Doctor says as applied to the Gya inscription will probably prove to be composed of fine Sanscrit, and to be more than 1800 years old. It may indeed have a still greater age, because some of the letters of the character No. 2 appear of a more illegible nature than those of the Gya sculpture, although manifestly of the same description. It must therefore have been engraven upon the column long before the two Persian lines before spoken of, which bear a date no farther back than 228 years, or A. H. 1014.

In the description of the Ellora Caves, in the 6th volume *As. Res.* no specimens of the inscription are given, but on reference to the fac similes of some of these in the 5th volume, I find that a few letters correspond with No. 2.

There is also I think a resemblance to the character No. 2, on a pillar at Buddal, which has been translated by Dr. WILKINS in the 1st volume *As. Res.* page 131, and a still greater similarity strikes me in the Monghir inscription, also translated by the same learned scholar in that volume.

I have thought it necessary to send a copy of part of the Gya inscription, which has been translated, together with the modern character written beneath it, as given by Dr. WILKINS in page 178, in order that it may be compared with the inscription No. 2, of this pillar. It seems to me to be exactly the same character, but perhaps less antique. Mr. HARRINGTON says, the pundits at Benares could not read the Gya inscription, but Dr. WILKINS has read it. Mr. HARRINGTON observes, that another inscription of one line only exists there, of a different character, and unintelligible. Perhaps this may be similar to No. 1, and it would be interesting to ascertain the fact through the aid of some of the correspondents of the *Journal*. Query. Has it any connection with the Greek character, to which No. 1 bears some similitude, in the Greek letters $\lambda \nu \sigma \epsilon \Delta \Gamma \Phi$ some of which are mentioned by Mr. STIRLING, at page 312, *As. Res.* volume XV. viz. the "ou, sigma, lambdu, chi, delta, epsilon, and

a something closely resembling a figure of the digamma*." The *Khandgir* inscription appears to resemble the Allahabad character exactly in my opinion.

Dr. W. says of this inscription No. 2, "The character is undoubtedly the most ancient of any that have hitherto come under my inspection;—it is not only dissimilar to that which is now in use, but even very materially different from that we find in inscriptions of eighteen hundred years ago; but though the writing be not modern, the language is pure Sanscrit, written in a long verse called *Sardoola vikrīta*, and consists of four pauses of nineteen syllables each, in this form,"—(which the Doctor gives)—they appear to be feet consisting of a mollassas, a pyrrhic, a trochee, a tribrach, a mollassas, a bacchias, and an iambus. The Doctor states that the metre was no small help in deciphering the words, and this will probably be found to be the case in the Allahabad inscription, as the letters composing the character, are chiefly equidistant from one another, without the appearance of stops. I have strong reason for thinking No. 2 to be verse, because several lines end with the same letter, which appears indicative of rhyme. It is probably of a mythological character. See also p. 357, recording the translation of a partly similar inscription found at the fort of Tanna.

The character at page 500 of this volume (xv. As. Res.) is not far different from the one line of inscription, No. 5, copied, as it appears, on the stone, viz. at right angles to the rest of the character, for both bear a peculiarly square appearance. See Alphabet of the same at p. 506, furnished by Mr. H. H. WILSON, from which this also may perhaps be deciphered†.

In the As. Res. vol. vi. page 447, Captain JOHN MACKENZIE sends a copy of the inscription found by him at Ceylon on a block of stone much corroded by time, but which he made out by tracing chunam, or lime water on the hollow characters indented in the rock, which rendered them legible on the dark ground of the stone. I think it would be a better plan in a similar case to pass a cloth or brush damped in lime-water, rapidly over the general surface of the stone, for when the lime dries white, every dark letter will appear distinctly contrasted with the white surface, because the letters themselves are not to be wetted, but only their projecting interstices.

The Ceylon inscription is probably old Sanscrit also, as it resembles No. 2 in some of the letters.

* See note at the end of this paper.—En.

† See Plate vi. at the right hand near the bottom.

Classification of the ancient character, No. 1.

Reference	Simple letter	united with the vowel marks.					with $\bar{n}$	other forms occurring
		$\bar{a}$?	$\bar{e}$?	$\bar{i}$?	$\bar{o}$?	$\bar{u}$?		
1	𑀓 32	𑀓 3	𑀓 11	𑀓 3	𑀓 2	𑀓 1	𑀓 ^o	𑀓 𑀓 𑀓 𑀓
2	𑀔 30	𑀔 12	𑀔 12	𑀔 15	𑀔 1	𑀔 2	𑀔	} 𑀔 𑀔 𑀔 𑀔 𑀔 } written 𑀔 by L ^e Burt
3	𑀕 2	𑀕 2	𑀕 12	𑀕 5	𑀕 1	𑀕 2	𑀕	
4	𑀖 30	𑀖 11	𑀖 4	𑀖 6	𑀖 4	𑀖 1	𑀖	𑀖 𑀖 𑀖 𑀖 (n ^o 2 with r ¹)
5	𑀗 26	𑀗 12	𑀗 12	𑀗 10	𑀗 2	𑀗 1	𑀗	𑀗 𑀗 𑀗
6	𑀘 1	𑀘 1	𑀘 2	𑀘 2	𑀘?	𑀘 1	𑀘	
7	𑀙 27	𑀙 6	𑀙 19	𑀙 3	𑀙?	𑀙 1	𑀙	𑀙 𑀙 𑀙
8	𑀚 29	𑀚 8	𑀚 8	𑀚 17	𑀚	𑀚 4	𑀚	𑀚 𑀚
9	𑀛 17	𑀛 8	𑀛 7	𑀛 22	𑀛 3	𑀛 2	𑀛	𑀛 𑀛 𑀛 ^o 𑀛
10	𑀜 20	𑀜 6	𑀜 10	𑀜 4	𑀜	𑀜 3	𑀜	(𑀜 in Burt)
11	𑀝 21	𑀝 7	𑀝 4	𑀝 4		𑀝 1	𑀝	𑀝 𑀝 𑀝 𑀝 𑀝 𑀝
12	𑀞 24	𑀞 1	𑀞 1	𑀞 1	𑀞	𑀞	𑀞	-
13	𑀟 17	𑀟 2	𑀟 1	𑀟 2		𑀟 2	𑀟	𑀟 𑀟
14	𑀠 20	𑀠				𑀠 ^o 9	𑀠	𑀠? 𑀠 (the rest effaced?)
15	𑀡 11	𑀡 6	𑀡 2	𑀡 7	𑀡 2	𑀡 2	𑀡	𑀡 𑀡 𑀡
16	𑀢 4	𑀢 2	𑀢 1	𑀢 2	𑀢 1	𑀢 1		𑀢 𑀢 𑀢
17	𑀣 9	𑀣 ^o 4		𑀣 7	𑀣 2	𑀣 1	𑀣	𑀣 𑀣
18	𑀤 5	𑀤 2	𑀤 4				𑀤	
19	𑀥 6	𑀥 1	𑀥?	𑀥	𑀥			𑀥 𑀥
20	𑀦 5	𑀦 6	𑀦					𑀦 𑀦 𑀦
21	𑀧 3			𑀧	𑀧			same as 21
22	𑀨 2	𑀨		𑀨	𑀨	𑀨		doubtful 𑀨
23	𑀩?	𑀩		𑀩	𑀩	𑀩		𑀩 𑀩 𑀩 𑀩 𑀩
24	𑀪	𑀪	𑀪	𑀪	𑀪			𑀪
25	𑀫 4	𑀫 3		𑀫 1	𑀫 1			half sixe
26	𑀬	𑀬		𑀬 1	𑀬	𑀬		ditto
27	𑀭 2			𑀭		𑀭?		ditto
28	𑀮 1	𑀮 3	𑀮	𑀮 2			𑀮	𑀮 do
29	.	:	:	:				
30	𑀯	𑀯	𑀯					

Compound of 𑀓+𑀔+𑀕?

The Initial word of 2 inscriptions on this &c
 𑀚 𑀓 𑀔 𑀕 𑀕
 on the Delhi Column. As. Res. VII. 180.

¶ The figures against each sign shew its frequency of occurrence on the Stone
 J.P. del.

In the inscription at Mahabalipuram*, *As. Res.* volume v. p. 75 to 80, a very few letters correspond with those in No. 2. Captain WILFORD, p. 135, says he was shewn a Sanscrit book containing many ancient alphabets, qr. at Benares?

Captain COLIN MCKENZIE states that there are unknown inscriptions on the pagoda at Perweettun, page 314, volume iii. Page 167, et seq. contain two translations, by Dr. WILKINS, of inscriptions from the Vindhya Mountains, but no specimens. Page 383 of ditto, is an inscription in the Malaga language engraven upon a silver plate, which was found in a cave near Islamabad by John Shore, Esq. (now Lord Teignmouth) but no specimen appears, which is to be regretted.

Volume iii. page 39. contains a specimen and translation, by Sir WILLIAM JONES, of a Sanscrit inscription from the Carnatic, not much like No. 2.

Mr. COLEBROOKE says at page 401, that Mr. WILKINS ascertained the date and scope of a Sanscrit inscription at Cintra in Portugal: see page 422, also, where the Canara language is stated to be mixed with Sanscrit in an inscription found in the Upper-Carnatic, some of the stanzas being supposed to be Pracrit; also that the junction of the three languages, Telinga, Mahratta and Canara, takes place some where about Beder. It is strange that a few of the natives here should say that No. 1, is Mahratta, and some that it must be Carnatic writing.

Page 224. "The ancient Canara has gone so much into disuse, that it was with difficulty I could get people to read it. An Alphabet will be yet communicated, as several books and ancient inscriptions are written in this character." Page 398 et seq.

The No. for August, 1833, of the *As. Soc. Journal*, shews in pages 387 et seq., several characters of the KAH GYUR similar to No. 2; see also vol. i. *Journal Asiatic Society*, page 276, where some Tibetan characters assimilate with it.

I have thus endeavoured to afford as much information as was in my power on the subject of the Allahabad pillar and inscription, and wish it could have been more satisfactory or ample; but I trust my endeavours will be considered in a favourable light, should the opinions I have expressed differ from those of others who must be so much better acquainted with the subject than I am.

A specimen of the stone accompanies.

* See note by Capt. TROYER: the Mahabalipur inscription is in the same character nearly as No. 2, and was of great use in deciphering it.—ED.

II.—*Note on Inscription No. 1 of the Allahabad Column.* By James Prinsep, Sec. &c.

When I requested the author of the preceding description to undertake the task, which he has so faithfully and carefully executed, I had but little anticipation of the valuable historical information that would reward the labour of transcribing the almost illegible inscriptions covering the surface of the Allahabad *lath*. Aware indeed that the only accurate data we possessed for adjusting the chronology of Indian princes were those derived from ancient monuments of stone; inscriptions on rocks and caves; or grants of land engraven on copper-plates, discovered accidentally in various parts of the country;—I could not see the highly curious column lying at Allahabad, falling to rapid decay, without wishing to preserve a complete copy of its several inscriptions: for the specimen of them, published in the seventh volume of the *Researches*, comprised but two or three lines; and was professedly intended to give only an idea of the different characters of the three (or, with the Persian, four) inscriptions. It is indeed greatly to be regretted that the task was not accomplished twenty or thirty years ago; for the ravages of time, or rather climate, have probably in that short period committed greater injuries on its surface, than during an equal number of centuries antecedent:—“The line in the printed specimen, near the Persian name Abdullah, is no longer to be seen on the stone,” says Lieut. BURT. The horizontal position of the pillar allows the rain to settle in the cavities of the letters, and soak into the stone itself, and this action alternating with the fierce heat to which it is exposed from the sun’s rays, has caused the outer surface of the stone to split and peel off in many places. Lying half buried in the ground also, the saltpetre, or other salt with which the soil is impregnated, must have had its share in the ruin of the prostrate monument. Many of the sandstone buildings in Benares, and indeed all over the country, exhibit the influence of this destructive agent; at the height of a few feet from the ground their surface is seen to peel off in thin flakes*, while the higher parts remain sharp and uninjured for ages. The Moghul emperor JEHANGIR was contented to engrave his name and proud descent in a belt through the middle of the most ancient inscription;—the English would rightly deprecate such profanation, but their own passive neglect has proved in a few short years even more destructive than the barbarous act of the Muhammedan despot.

* The effect may be produced by the crystallization of the deliquescent salt lodged on the stone at that height, and marked by a zone of damp; the heat of the day would evaporate the moisture, and cause the salt to crystallize, which would split the stone just as the freezing of water in cold climates produces the same injury to buildings.

We have however before us what remains at this time of its interesting contents, and must hasten to make them known for the satisfaction of the antiquarian and the Sanscrit scholar. There are, as Lieut. BURT has fully described, three principal types of inscription, exclusive of the modern Persian sculpture.

The two first and most important I have carefully reduced from the facsimiles presented to the Asiatic Society, so as to suit the pages of the Journal.—The third, No. 3 of Lieut. BURT, consists merely of detached names and dates in modern Nagari, Bhaka, Marhatta, &c., and though the longest, is the least interesting, and is not worth the trouble of transcribing. A few of the dates are enumerated in the foregoing account.

No. 2, as pointed out by Lieut. BURT, is identical in character with the Gya inscription decyphered by Dr. WILKINS. It was made over at the meeting of the Society to Captain TROYER, Secretary of the Sanscrit College, who has been fortunate enough, with the aid of MADHAVA RAY PANDIT, the librarian, to decypher many parts of it: and their examination has developed the names of several princes, and particularly of CHANDRAGUPTA, perhaps the one most earnestly desired by the Indian antiquarian, because of its connection with an epoch in the histories of the western world. Dr. WILKINS had imagined the Gya character to be as ancient as the Christian era, which will be confirmed, if the CHANDRAGUPTA spoken of be the same of whom ARRIAN speaks. Some doubt may again arise from the discovery of his name on a monument at Allahabad, with regard to the position of his capital, a point that has only lately been considered to be set at rest by the identification of Palibothra with *Pataliputra* or Patna. The name of SAMUDRAGUPTA as a fourth descendant of CHANDRAGUPTA is not found in the Hindu catalogues of the MAURYA dynasty, although there can be no doubt of the reading on the column. I have extracted the name and titles of CHANDRAGUPTA, and placed them in the plate under the alphabetical key, to shew that it has been faithfully rendered by the pandit.

One other Raja of the same name occurs among the Ajmeer or Rajputana princes in the seventh century, but here also the descendants are of different appellations. The only argument which occurs to me as favoring the latter date, is the great similarity between the Sanscrit character of the inscription and the Tibetan, (noticed also by Lieutenant BURT): the alphabet of which, according to Mr. CSOMA DE KOROS, was adopted from the Sanscrit in the seventh century. Many letters are indeed identical and of the same phonic value, as will be evident on comparing the following with the alphabet in plate VI:—

क kh, ग g, च ch, छ ch, ज j, त t, द d, न n, प p, य ph, ब b, व v, ह h, य y, ल l, श sh: also the whole of the vowel marks [^]i, u, [˘]e, [˘]o: the sub-

joined letters *r* and *y*; as, ꣳ *dra* and ꣳ *pya*, and the *vazur* or subjoined *w* or *v*, as ꣳ *dv* or *do*.

Other similarities might be pointed out, but these are the most striking: the mode of expressing the long *á* also at that period, by a short dash at the top of the letter, may explain the omission of this character in the Tibetan alphabet. Captain TROYER notices the omission of many letters* (*gh, jh, &c.*) which are equally wanting in the Tibetan alphabet. However, the identity here noticed does not necessarily detract from the antiquity of the inscription, or prevent its applying to the earlier CHADRAGUPTA; since the same character was probably in use for many centuries. When or where it gave place to the more modern Nagari would be a curious and interesting subject of investigation.

However ancient the inscription No. 2 may be, it is very certain that the character No. 1 boasts a still higher antiquity. This may I think be proved—first, by the position it occupies on the Allahabad column, as well as on that of Delhi, called *Feroz's lath*: in both it is the principal, and as it were the original inscription, the others being subsequently added, perhaps on some occasions of triumph or visit to the spot. Secondly, the simplicity of this character and the limited number of radicals, denote its priority to the more complicated and refined system afterwards adopted; while thirdly, the very great rarity of its occurrence on ancient monuments, and the perfect ignorance which prevails regarding its origin in the earliest Persian historians, who mention the lath of FEROSH SHAH, confirm its belonging to an epoch beyond the reach of native research. The only other inscriptions identical in character which have been met with in India, are I believe that of the lath of BHIM SEN in Sarun†, and that of the Khandgiri rocks in Orissa, of which a facsimile is given by Mr. STIRLING in the *Researches*, vol. xv. page 314. The Ellora and other cave inscriptions appear to be considerably modified from it, and in fact more to resemble No. 2 of the Allahabad column; and the latter inscription has so many points of resemblance, that it may be fairly traced to a derivation from the former.

It is not yet ascertained, whether the language this character, No. 1, expresses is Sanscrit. The rare occurrence of double letters, the omission of the initial *Sri*; the want of any symbol with a subjoined *y* to correspond with ꣳ , the inflexion of the possessive case which occurs so repeatedly, and is so distinct, in the Sanscrit text No. 2; are arguments against the supposition: but the similarity of the character and of the vowel marks are as much in its favor.

* See page 118.

† Has any copy of this inscription been published? Mr. STIRLING mentions it, but I do not find it in the *Researches*.

Mr. STIRLING has suggested as a remarkable circumstance that many letters of the No. 1 type resemble Greek characters, and he instances the "ou, sigma, lambda, chi, delta, epsilon, and a something closely resembling the figure of the digamma." This resemblance is, however, entirely accidental, and the genus of the alphabet can I think be satisfactorily shewn to have no connection whatever with the Greek. To enable us to determine this point, I have taken the trouble of analyzing carefully the whole of the inscription from Lieut. BURR's manuscript, classifying those forms which seemed to be derived from the same radix.

Proceeding in this manner I soon perceived that each radical letter was subject to five principal inflections, the same in all, corresponding in their nature and application with the five vowel marks of the ancient Sanscrit No. 2. This circumstance alone would be sufficient to prove that the alphabet is of the Sanscrit family, whatever the language may be. In the accompanying plate (Pl. V.) I have arranged the letters and their inflections so as to exhibit every form which occurs on the column, placing numbers against each, expressive of the frequency of its occurrence. From a cursory inspection of this plate it will immediately be seen that the supposed *sigma* is but the first inflection of the 13th letter: the *epsilon* and *digamma*, are the same inflections of the 18th and 11th characters: while the *ou* and *lambda* (1 and 2) are themselves subject to all the inflections like the rest, and are consequently primitive or simple letters, of a system quite different from the Greek.

The number of alphabetical symbols is small, compared with those of modern systems founded on the Sanscrit: of the thirty, several have not been found subject to inflection; these may be initial vowels. The circle, square, and triangle are of a smaller size in general than the rest, and may be affixes: but of this and of the powers of the letters, I cannot pretend to offer any conjectures at the present moment. Many of the literal forms undoubtedly bear a close resemblance to those of No. 2, and to those of the Mahabalipur alphabet, decyphered by Dr. BABINGTON; and one might almost be tempted to point out successively the *s*, *d*, *dr*, *v*, *b*, *ch*, *j*, *g*, *t*, *l*, from their analogy to the known letters in the foregoing scheme. It is better however to say nothing on this head, until we are prepared to apply the scheme to the unravelling of a portion of the legend. For this purpose, one word offers a very convenient test: it is the initial word of both parts of the Allahabad inscription (see pl. V.);—of all the four inscriptions on the Delhi column; and it also occurs a second time on the east side. I have inserted it at the foot of Plate VI. It will probably be found to be some term of invocation, though essentially different from the *Sri* of the Hindus.

As one mode of aiding the investigation of the powers of the unknown alphabet, supposing the language expressed to be Sanscrit, I had the letters in a page of the *Bhatti Kāvya* classified and counted, to compare with the enumeration in Plate VI. They were as follows :

त	93 times	म	33 times	व	9 times	भू	3 times	ट	0 times
य	57	प	30	इ	9	ई	3	क	0
न	51	श	25	ह	6	ए	2	ठ	0
र	51	ल	22	ड	6	अ	2	ड	0
क	45	थ	15	घ	5	ख	1	फ	0
स	44	च	14	ध	9	फ	1	ढ	0
द	43	ग	12	ण	5	उ	1	ञ	0
व	41	ष	11	ज	3	च	1		

I also made the same classification of one page of the *Feroz lath* inscription, which I found to agree pretty well with the table prepared from that of Allahabad. There is one marked difference, which may be due perhaps to the copyist :—I allude to the separation of the words in the former, which does not appear to be the case in Lieut. BURT'S transcript.

It would require an accurate acquaintance with many of the learned languages of the East, as well as perfect leisure and abstraction from other pursuits, to engage upon the recovery of this lost language ; but when its simplicity of vocables is compared with the difficulties of the Persepolitan, or cuneiform character, lately decyphered by GROTEFEND and St. MARTIN, or the more abstruse hieroglyphics of Egypt attempted by YOUNG and CHAMPOLLION, it seems almost a stigma on the learned of our own country that this should have remained so long an enigma to scholars ; and the object of the present notice is to invite fresh attention to the subject, lest the indefatigable students of Bonn or Berlin should run away with the honor of first making it known to the learned world.

III.—*Remarks upon the second Inscription of the Allahabad Pillar.* By Captain A. Troyer, A. D. C. Sec. Sanscrit College, &c.

[Read at the Meeting of the 20th March.]

An alphabet of the inscription No. 2, copied from the Allahabad pillar, compared with the Deva-nagari, was compiled by MADHAVA RAO, the head Librarian of the Sanscrit College. It will be seen from the annexed copy of it, (Plate VI.) that eight of the consonants, namely, घ (g'h), ङ (j'h), ञ (n), ट (t'), ठ (t'h), ड (d'), ढ (d'h), and three of the vowels इ ई ऊ (i, í, ú,) could not be found.

The alphabet of the Allahabad inscription offers certainly a great apparent similarity to that of a part of the Gya inscription, examined by Dr. WILKINS, [As. Res. vol. i. page 279.] as pointed out by Licut. BURT, of the Engineers. It almost entirely coincides with that of some inscriptions on the rocks of Mahámalaipur, (vide Trans. of Royal As. Soc. vol. ii. part 1, Plates 13, 14.) Notwithstanding this similarity common to a great number of Indian alphabets, it is not yet easy to fix the value of each letter of an ancient writing, in such a manner as to preclude the possibility of a doubt.

It was principally the alphabet of the Mahámalaipur inscriptions that enabled MADHAVA RAO to transcribe in Devanagari characters, the remains of the inscription copied from the pillar at Allahabad. This consists of 30 lines. More than a moiety of the first 13 lines is entirely peeled off; the other 17 are fuller, but evidently more or less cut off at the right extremity, and all with many intervening chasms.

An even slight examination of the transcript made in Devanagari characters is sufficient to find a number of Sanscrit words, and the whole inscription may without hesitation be pronounced to be Sanscrit. In the accompanying paper, the translation of the Sanscrit words, which could without difficulty be found in each line, is given. Scarce any change has been made in the words of the transcript, except in a few instances, such a correction as is too often indispensable even in not inaccurate manuscripts. These few changes are marked above the lines.

As the frequent and wide disjunction of words, the terminations of which are mostly wanted, renders it impossible to fix the relative sense of each word, as well as to determine the general purport of the whole, any conjectural labour in changing vocables and supplying deficiencies would have been hopeless.

So much only appears indubitable from the words themselves, that they are encomiastic epithets of a Raja, the name of whom, if satisfactorily made out, might furnish an historical datum of no small importance.

Names are really found in the 17th, 18th, and 21st lines which seem insignificant; not so those in the 25th and 26th line, which happen to be more complete and connected than the others: thus we have in the twenty-fifth line;—"of the great-grandson of SRI CHANDRAGUPTA, the great Raja, of the grandson of the great Raja SRI YAGNAKACHA, of the son of the great Raja, the first (supreme) Raja (Adhiraja) SRI CHANDRAGUPTA :"

and in the twenty-sixth line, "of the son of the daughter of LICH-CH'HA VIKRITI of the family of MAHADIVYA KUMARA—of the great Raja, the supreme Raja SRI SAMUDRAGUPTA, whose fame caused by the conquest

of the whole earth, increasing and expanding throughout the whole ground of the earth, was equalling TRIDASÁPATI (INDRA)."

The name of CHANDRAGUPTA repeated here twice, as that of the great-grandfather, and that of the father of a Raja, cannot fail to excite attention.

According to the Hindee genealogies of the *Vishnupurana* and other books, CHANDRAGUPTA, a son, or at least a relative, of NANDA, founded a dynasty (called by his name, and also the *Maurya* dynasty, from his mother MURA), of 10 kings, who reigned during 137 years from the year 1598 to 1735 of the *Kaliyug*, (from 1504 to 1367 before our era,) in *Magadha*, the capital of which was *Palibothra*. It needs scarce be repeated that the Indian name CHANDRAGUPTA (the moon-protected) was found to be the same with SANDRA-COTTUS, or SANDROKUPTOS mentioned by the Greek historians. It is also known that from the similarity of these names, an identity of the persons of the contemporary of ALEXANDER and ally of SELEUCUS Nicator, and of the before-mentioned founder of the Indian dynasty of that name was supposed, and that a whole system of Indian chronology was made dependent upon this supposition.

No disquisition upon this important and extensive subject will here be expected, so much less as the imperfect remains of the inscription here examined furnish no vestige of a date, nor any other data which may lead our conjectures towards, if not fix, a historical fact. It would be adventurous to assert that the CHANDRAGUPTA of line 25th, was the founder of the Maurya dynasty: all that appears in the inscription is, that a Raja SAMUDRAGUPTA (the sea-protected) was a descendant in the 4th generation of a CHANDRAGUPTA.

It is further to be remarked, that the name of the second CHANDRAGUPTA and that of SAMUDRAGUPTA are joined with the title *Adhirája*, supreme Raja, and not with that of *Chakravartti*, or emperor of the world, always assumed by the ruler of India. We may therefore infer that the Adhirájas of the inscription did not pretend to universal, although but titular, sovereignty; but may have been only counted among the many Rajas who at all times divided India among themselves. It was probably by their flatterers that the conquest of a few provinces was made the *conquest of the whole world*; in which expression, found entire among the ruins of so many others, nothing else but a monument of empty vanity was preserved.

Translation of Sanscrit Words of the Allahabad Inscription.

LINE I.

— II.—1. minding sacrifice of the gods. 2. for the sake of a better state.

— III.—3. counting the low. 4. knowing good qualities. 5. in heaven. ..

6 and 7. enjoying a poet's fame and a kingdom.

- LINE IV..... 8. with servants and family.....
- V. 9. said by his son.....
- VI.—10. in his actions of a never changing mind.....
- VII.—11. Most valiant,..... whose foot approaching duly I salute.
- VIII.—12. in the battle,..... with his own arm vanquishing always.
- IX.—13. with high.. .. expanded—minds.
- X.
- XI.
- XII.—14. fame as seen by men (illumed) by the rays of the moon...
- XIII.—15. active in the road, a poet's intellect and power proceeding. . .
- XIV.—16. of Brahma... of the dextrous in hundred avatars—his own arm's mighty strength praised.
- XV.—17. arrow..... 18. family 19. good name.
- XVI..... 20. MAHENDRA'S worshipper.. 21. MAHENDRA'S mountain.
- XVII.—22. NILARAJA to be known by words.. preserver of elephant's armor.. UGRASENA, DEVARASHTA. 23. from DHANANJAYA down all southern chartered kings taking.
- XVIII.—24. VAMATILANA GADATTA CHANDRA VASU
- 25. all giving rent.
- XIX. 26. by neighbouring kings. ..
- XX.—27. destroyer of PRACHANDA SASANA (of a terrible commander).. 28. Destroyer of a kingly family,.. .. . 29. whose fame is spread throughout all countries, son of a god.
- XXI.—30. all governing his own humble faith. .. . giver of one hundred thousand.
- XXII.—31. ground of battle, fame of kings,.. .. 32. Of unpararelled faith, .. who by the strength of his own arm conquered more than one king.
- XXIII.—33. Lord of the unfortunate.. .. 34. of him who was inaugurated the most eminent of poets.
- XXIV.—35. sharp intellect, high understanding.. Gandharva—TRIDASAPATI (INDRA) 36. By heavenly poetical works composed by learned men of him who was inaugurated the most eminent of Rajas .. 37. of a magnanimous conduct.
- XXV.—38. of him whose mind is formed by time and action only in the palace of the world .. of the great-grandson of CHANDRAGUPTA, of the grandson of the great Raja SRI YAGNAKACHA, and of the son of the great Raja, the first (supreme) Raja (Adhiraja) SRI CHANDRAGUPTA.
- XXVI.—39. of the son of the daughter of LIC-CH'HA VIKRITI, of the family of MAHADIVYA KUMARA .. of the great Raja, the supreme Raja (Adhiraja) SRI SAMUDRAGUPTA, whose fame caused by the conquest of the whole earth increased and expanded throughout the whole ground of the earth was equalling TRIDASAPATI, (INDRA.)
- XXVII.—40. going to the house.. .. 41 gift by arm's strength, favor, weapons, words increase over and over, all-serving, jewel desiring fame
- XXVIII.—41. PASUPATI (SIVA) purifying the three worlds. .. .
- XXIX. 43. Of the son skilled in peace and war young prince.
- XXX.—44. the supreme king 45. the chief of punishment (literally the chief of staffs, perhaps police-officer)' by TILABHADANTA.

Transcript of the Allahabad inscription, No. 3. in Deva-Nagari characters.

LINE

- 1 (the first line illegible.)
- 2 मस्यक यगचेतसखमनसः शसतरार्थम. . ल. . ल. . नि
 1 सु 2
- 3 व्यश्रिविक्तौ धान्त धगणित गुणज्ञउतनेचकत्व . . वर्लोकैस्य कवतकीर्त्तिं राच्यं भुनक्तौ
 3 4 स्व 5 ख्व 6 7
- 4 तुपुग भवपशनैनक्त. . नरैमभिः सभ्येसि सभ्यत्पकुस्रजमननवां
 8
- 5 स्रउव्य. . तेन. . ध. . गउणतलिच्छिणवक्षस्यः पुत्रभिहितानिधिकनिग्वि
 9
- 6 स्वकम्पस्यनैकन्यमनसदृ. . शन्यद्भुतोद्भिन्नाउसंभवेरासदधम. . . .
 10-10
- 7 वीर्यन्तम शिकच शरणम पगत यस्यदत्तेप्रणमेपरि. . . .
 11-11
- 8 संग्रासेसखभुजविजितनित्यममबासकराः. . श्रयोमानप्र. . . .
 12 12
- 9 तो. . . . तुङ्गैःस्फर. . रारसस्तुफलैर्भनोभिः पुश्र्यपुव. .
 13 13
- 10 रेद्वेलोदत. . रविर्धर. . सुदेकेनायिन ननगिसुध
- 11 ग्राउयगेचकौतुकुलज यक्तेहपाद
 14
- 12 ध द्रचोर नाःशशकिरण चयः कीर्त्तयसुप्रतंनरदृश्यते कदप्रगम्य
 15 15 15
- 13 सक्तमार्गःकविमतिविभवात्सरणं चपुकव्यकोनस्य . . . नम्य
 16 16
- 14 वेधसःपर शतावतरणदक्षस्य स्वभुजबलपराक्तमर. . न्ध. . प्रससितोमर
 17 18 19
- 15 भस्यपु नाराचवोतस्त्रि कव्या नक प्रहरण विज. . . कुल. . . त. . . श्भननाम
 दायपटितकन्तरव . . यकवि . . वसुक्तक
- 20
- 16 क्क. . सरक. . महेन्द्रमहकन्तारक. . व्या. . राजक्क राजकम राज पराक महेन्द्र
 गरिक. . रकस्मरत्तिरा. . पत्तकरासनकसनग्रहजनितप्रत श्र हभाग्यस्य
 22 22 22 22 23
- 17 नीलराजवाजेय कक्षसिखर्मपालककोप्रसनद्वराष्टककु. . रकोस्थलपरक धनञ्जय
 23
 प्रभृति सर्वदक्षिण पदराजग्रहण. . . तः परिचकीकतसर्व्य विकराजस्य
- 24
- 18 . . वामतिलनामदत्तचन्द्रव. . ग . . श्रतिन्नागनग नाश्रुतनन्दि लवययनकार्यवर्त्त
 25
 राजप्रस. . द्वर. . क्षप्ररोचमउरिकदिभिग्य सर्वकरदान . . करणप्रणभागमन
- 26
- 19 समत दवक कामजपनदालकृतपुणंप्रत्यन्त वृत्तिभिः. . लव. . नयन दयमाद्रक
 र. . ससनक. . क. . कवि यद्दानसहिशकम. . षः . . सहजक . . भिश्य . .

- LINE श 27 28
 20. . . परिणषितप्रचण्डशसनस्य . . कभू . . रा तुन्तराजवंशप्रति ण तनियो
 टि 29
 गंतयशसःद्वपुत्र . . सुरधरणी न्तस्य . . शृथिव्यामप्रतिरथस्य
- 21 सर्व् . . पवसिभिरात्मनिवादनक क्योदयनदानगहकद स्वविनयभक्तिशामन
 चनद्दोय . . . वकनर्थ प्रवन तिमात्र . . शो . . शृधदुदयस्यनकम्पुवतौनक
 30
 शतसहस्रप्रदायिन
- 22 . . शतलंछतनकगुणग . . स्तिभि . . रणतलप्र . . न्यनरपतिकीर्त्तिःस सन्निदयंप्रक
 31 31
 हस्यहः पदस स्थभक्तमस्य स्थभजवलविजितनकनरपतिवि
 32 42 1
 वप्रत्य नित्यव्यप्र . . यकपदस्य
- 23 . . दीननय . . रजनद्वरणसन्नादी . . भ्यपगनमप्रस्यविग्रहवतादाकनगहस्यधनद
 33
 34
 णन् . . कःप्रतिष्ठितकविराजश्रेष्ठस्य सचिर . . तच्यतनकदतोदायरितस्य
- 24 निशित विदा प्रमतिक गांधर्व लहितो वीरोप्र त्रिदशपति गाह उनिरदा
 35 35 35
 26 सु I I
 . . द्विदज्जनशैव्य नाककव्यक्तियभिः प्रतिष्ठितराजश्रेष्ठस्यसचिरा . . तच्यतनकद
 37
 तौदारचरितस्य
- 25 समयक्तिय नविधान मात्रमानसस्य लोकधान्नी . . वस्य . . महाराज श्रीगुप्त
 38 38
 प्रपौत्रस्य महाराजश्रीय कचपात्रस्य . . महाराजाधिराज श्रीचन्द्रगुप्त पुत्रस्य
- 39 च तनदौहित्यस्य I 39
- 26 छिन्श्विर्वाहिस्यमहादयकुमारदयाम . . न्तस्य महाराजाधिराज श्री समुद्रगुप्तस्य
 सर्वशृथिवीविजय जनितोदयव्याप्त निखिलान्वनीतल कीर्त्तिमितसिदशपतिः
 40 41
- 27 भवनगमनवप्रक . . तसुखविचरणमाच . . णः । वभुवोमा रययु तसन्मयस्य प्रदान
 42
 43
 44
 45
 भुजविक्रम प्रशम शस्त वाक्योदय उपर्युपरिसर्वा यद्वित मनिमार्गयशः
 पुनाति भुवनत्रयं पशुपतं . . न्तमहतिरोधपरिमा . . मिवपुण्ड्रप्रच . . तवकाय
 . . स . . वभंजनपादानुदासस्य . . सभपुपरिस . . णनय . . हितमतिः
- 29 शृष्ट . . पुक्तिकस्यमहादण्डनायक वभूति . . पुत्रस्यसन्धिविग्रहिककुमारामा
 त्यम कडरि स्यसर्वभूतहृतसखायस्य
- 30 सनद्धितच परमभट्टारक पदान तम दण्डनायकतिलभदंतेन ।

[The figures in the interlineations point out the words (beneath them) translated in the foregoing page: the letters similarly situated are suggested corrections of the text.]